

A combined mindfulness–prolonged chewing intervention reduces weight, food craving, and emotional eating

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Abstract

Objective: Conventional weight loss programs that induce a calorie deficit mostly fail in long-term weight reduction and disadvantageous eating styles often remain unchanged. Mindfulness interventions therefore redirect the focus away from the weight loss goal and toward the process of eating itself. By eating more mindfully, at a slower pace, and with an enhanced focus on bodily sensations, participants might not only indirectly reduce their daily calorie intake but also eat less craving- and stress-driven. **Method:** This study randomized participants to either intervention ($n=23$) or waitlist group ($n=23$) to investigate the effectiveness of a four-session mindfulness and prolonged chewing intervention. Dependent variables were body mass index (BMI), food craving, as well as emotional, external, and intuitive eating. **Results:** Across the eight weeks of intervention, significant group \times measurement time interactions pointed to decreases in BMI and disadvantageous eating styles (food cravings, emotional, and external eating) and an increase in intuitive eating in the intervention group. Weight loss in the intervention group was maintained after a 4-week follow up. **Conclusion:** A combination of mindfulness and a specific chewing training that increases awareness of satiety strongly impacted energy intake and related eating styles. Such interventions obviate loss-oriented calorie reduction and foster enjoyment and focused tasting of foods. Conventional weight loss diets might incorporate such brief interventions in more long-term dieting trials.

Public Health Statement: Weight control is central to modern eating. Modifying how to eat rather than what to eat adds a new perspective to weight control. This study showed that prolonged chewing embedded in supporting mindfulness exercises not only benefits body weight but also supports the development of healthy eating styles.

Keywords: obesity, mindfulness, prolonged chewing, food craving, emotional eating

Introduction

A sedentary lifestyle and an energy-dense diet comprised of food high in sugar and saturated fats have led to increasing prevalence rates of obesity (WHO, 2015). This often causes massive health problems, including diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and cancer (Guh et al., 2009). Bariatric surgeries are effective but highly invasive and expensive (Chang et al., 2014). Moreover, conventional behavioral treatments mostly fail in long-term weight reduction: dieters struggle to maintain new eating patterns, give in to food cravings, and consequently regaining most of their weight after a year (Butryn, Webb, & Wadden, 2011). In certain individuals, weight loss programs might actually *favor* weight problems and pathological eating patterns, such as binge eating and bulimic symptoms (Goldschmidt, Wall, Loth, Le Grange, & Neumark-Sztainer, 2012).

Thus, more recent approaches moved away from the loss-orientation implicated in calorie-restrictive diets and take several psychological determinants of (over)eating into account (Hemmingsson, 2014): Rather than asking about the *what* and the *how much* to eat or how to expend energy, the *process of eating itself* is addressed. *Mindfulness-based trainings (MBT)* teach individuals to become fully aware of the present moment by concentrating on bodily sensations, including hunger and satiety. Through this increased awareness, healthier eating habits become viable. Additionally, *decentering* exercises aim to broaden one's perspective and view subjective experiences (such as cravings and emotions) as impermanent and fleeting. Through reducing 'mindless' food cue reactivity, decentering exercises can thus decrease food cravings (Keesman, Aarts, Hafner, & Papiés, 2017). This mindset facilitates the development of a non-judgmental acceptance of the own perception of reality (Bishop et al., 2004), including negative emotions and stress. Regarding food intake, this translates to eating in correspondence with homeostatic signals and actual energy needs. *MBT* therefore indirectly encourages an intuitive eating style, that is, eating in response to physiological hunger and

satiety cues rather than situational and emotional cues (Tylka, 2006). Through awareness and decentering, individuals not only become less responsive to external food cues, stress, negative emotions, or cravings as triggers of food intake (Tapper, 2017) but also learn to pay undivided attention to the process of eating (Warren, Smith, & Ashwell, 2017).

Largely in parallel, and with little intersection with the emerging field of *MbT*, an old idea developed by Fletcher (1849–1919) was rediscovered. Central is the advice to chew food for up to 50-100 times in order to liquefy foods in the mouth, which normally does not happen until food reaches the stomach (Barnett, 1992). This leads to a slowing of food intake and a focus on sensory experiences, which ultimately reduces energy intake, as confirmed by a recent meta-analysis (Robinson et al., 2014). Interestingly, such *prolonged chewing (PCh)* can not only slow food intake but also increase taste perception, as the surface of food increases when bitten into smaller pieces, which goes along with enhanced flavor experience (Smith, 1971). This might enrich the hedonic food experience and confer a preference for high quality foods. Further, changes in biochemical mechanisms can be observed, including a higher accessibility of nutrients and alterations in gut hormones that regulate food intake (Miquel-Kergoat, Azais-Braesco, Burton-Freeman, & Hetherington, 2015).

These approaches obviate the concept of any ‘forbidden foods’ or intake reduction and related experiences of deprivation. An ideal prerequisite for establishing *PCh* routines might be the undivided attention devoted to eating (or any other sensation) in *MbT*, which has gone largely unnoticed. Both approaches may circumvent prominent deprivation experiences during weight loss dieting which can trigger pronounced food cravings (Blechert, Naumann, Schmitz, Herbert, & Tuschen-Caffier, 2014). On the contrary: They emphasize eating pleasure and, by doing so, increase intuitive eating and discourage some frequent problematic eating patterns in overweight and dieting individuals, such as emotional and binge eating (O’Reilly, Cook, Spruijt-Metz, & Black, 2014).

Despite promising initial findings for *MbT* in weight management (Tapper, 2017), evidence is rather scarce. Existing studies were mostly limited to convenience samples or did not include appropriate control groups or follow-up measures (Warren et al., 2017). Furthermore, the research lines of *MbT* and *PCh* have—to our knowledge—not been explicitly synergistically combined. Thus, the present study integrated *MbT* techniques with *PCh* training, including in-session chewing practices and an emphasis on gustatory and sensory experience. A sample of predominantly overweight, weight loss-motivated individuals was randomized to either a *MbT/PCh* eight-week intervention group (IG) or a waitlist control group (WG). Although energy intake or physical activity was never emphasized during training, we expected a decrease of body mass index (BMI) in the IG only. In addition, we expected the intervention to reduce food cravings, as well as emotional and external eating while increasing intuitive eating.

Method

Participants and Procedure

Via social media and face-to-face, individuals motivated to improve their eating behavior or lose weight were recruited for an *MbT/PCh* eating intervention. All interested 46 individuals were included and randomized to either IG or WG by drawing lots. Two WG participants dropped out before the (delayed) cross-over intervention started; one participant in the IG stopped due to medical reasons (unrelated to the intervention). However, all randomized participants were included in an intention-to-treat approach.¹

¹ Analyzing only intervention completers did not change pattern or significance of the Time×Group interactions (BMI: $p < .001$; trait food craving: $p < .001$; external eating: $p = .022$; emotional eating: $p = .005$; intuitive eating: $p < .001$).

The study was approved by the ethics committee of the University of Salzburg. After being informed about study goals and procedures and being given the opportunity to ask questions, participants provided informed consent. Participants were compensated through free healthy snacks and drinks during *PCh* practices along with information material. At baseline (BL), demographic characteristics and questionnaire scores on craving and emotional, external, and intuitive eating were assessed (see Table 1). One week later, the first group session took place for participants in the IG.

Table 1

Questionnaires used to assess emotional eating, external eating, food craving, and intuitive eating. Across measurement points, internal consistency was high (all Cronbach's $\alpha > .80$).

Measure	Content
Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire (DEBQ German; 30 items; Grunert, 1989)	Subscales for emotional eating (e.g., “When I’m irritated, I have the desire to eat.”; 10 items), and external eating (e.g., “When I see others eating, I eat more than usual.”; 10 items) to assess a more intuitive and mindful food intake.
Food Cravings Questionnaire-Trait-reduced (FCQ-T-r German; 15 items; Meule, Hermann, & Kübler, 2014)	Statements on trait-level food cravings (e.g., “I find myself preoccupied with food.” or “If I give in to a food craving, all control is lost.”).
Intuitive Eating Scale-2 (IES-2 German; 23 items; van Dyck, Herbert, Happ, Kleveman, & Vögele, 2016)	Assessment of the ability to attend to body signals regarding hunger and satiety to determine whether or not to eat (e.g., “I trust my body to tell me when I should eat.”).

Group session 1 (week 1) covered information on mindful eating and included a ‘body scan’, during which attention is verbally guided through the whole body, as well as a 10-20

minutes *PCh* session, where various healthy food items (e. g. carrots, bread) as well as personal favorite foods were chewed. Participants were instructed to eat with eyes closed and to only swallow completely liquefied food, fully concentrating on taste and tongue reflexes. They received written material, including a *MbT* diary for all main meals and were instructed to regularly practice *MbT* and eating exercises at home.

Individual session 1 (week 3) included a 20-minute body scan and standardized psychoeducation on stress and emotional eating. Furthermore, possible individual (over)eating behavior problems were discussed and a personal eating behavior goal that went beyond losing weight was set. A *PCh* was held in case participants were hungry. Halfway through the intervention, both groups provided data for posttest 2 (T2, week 4).

Individual session 2 (week 5) started with a decentering exercise, guiding participants to see oneself from an outside perspective to notice detrimental thoughts and distance oneself from them. Next, solutions for possible problems with *MbT* and *PCh* in daily life were discussed. Lastly, participants chose a mindfulness exercise (e.g. progressive muscle relaxation, imaginary journey, meditation, yoga, or a walk) and discussed how to incorporate the acquired skills further into daily life. Reminder SMS were sent in the following weeks.

Group session 2 (week 8) started with *PCh*, before participants shared their experiences and satisfaction with the now completed intervention and completing measures for posttest 3 (T3, week 8). The following week, the WG started the identical intervention. Both groups filled out a follow-up questionnaire 4 weeks post intervention. See Figure 1 for an overview of the study flow.

Figure 1. Overview of study intake, randomization, groups, treatment, and measures. Intervention groups were split in half for the group sessions, proceeding with an offset of one week. All sessions and were held by the same trainer.

Statistical Analysis

Separate 3×2, Time (BL, T2, T3)×Group (IG and WG) ANOVAs with repeated measures were used to analyze treatment effect for each dependent variable (i.e., BMI, food craving emotional eating, external eating, intuitive eating). Significant Time×Group interactions were followed by Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons using mean

differences (*MD*) between BL and T2 as well as between BL and T3 for both groups separately. Greenhouse-Geisser correction for non-sphericity was used with whole-number degrees of freedom being reported.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 shows that at baseline age, gender, current dieting, and all dependent variables did not differ between groups (all $ps > .050$), indicating successful randomization. Compared to other samples (Meule, 2018), trait food craving values were rather high across groups in the present sample ($M=50.2$, $SD=16.3$) while external ($M=35.7$, $SD=6.76$), emotional ($M=28.4$, $SD=8.37$), and intuitive ($M=3.06$, $SD=0.53$) eating were in the normal range.

Table 2

Baseline characteristics with means (M) and standard deviations (SD) or Number of individuals (N) and percentage of group (%) for intervention group (IG) and waitlist control group (WG).

Variable	IG	WG	p-values
	(N=23)	(N=23)	
	<i>M (SD)</i>	<i>M (SD)</i>	
Age (in years)	32.0 (10.3)	38.9 (15.2)	.081
Body mass index	26.8 (4.58)	28.6 (4.96)	.200
Trait food craving	54.8 (14.3)	45.7 (17.2)	.057
Emotional eating	30.0 (7.35)	26.8 (9.17)	.196
External eating	37.1 (6.84)	34.2 (6.49)	.140
Intuitive eating	2.92 (.450)	3.21 (0.58)	.069
Variable	N (%)	N (%)	
Gender (female)	17 (73.9)	17 (73.9)	1.00
Currently dieting	14 (60.9)	11 (47.8)	.375

Intervention effects

BMI. The 3×2, Time (BL, T2, T3)×Group (IG and WG) ANOVA for BMI revealed a main effect of Time, $F(2,88)=18.7$, $p<.001$, $\eta_p^2=.298$, but no main effect of Group, $F(1,44)=2.45$, $p=.125$, $\eta_p^2=.053$. The Time effect was modulated by a Time×Group interaction, $F(2,88)=11.0$, $p<.001$, $\eta_p^2=.201$. For the IG, a BMI decrease was significant between BL and T2, $MD=0.51$, $p<.001$, 95% CI [.194, .821] and between BL and T3, $MD= 1.12$, $p<.001$, 95% CI [.654, 1.58] but not for the WG, both $MDs\leq 0.25$, $ps\geq .210$. BMI loss in the IG was maintained during the 4-weeks follow-up, $t(19)<1.00$ (Figure 2A).

Figure 2. Means and standard errors for intervention vs. waitlist control group across time (baseline vs. posttest 2 vs. posttest 3) for (A) body mass index, (B) Food Cravings Questionnaire-Trait-reduced, (C) Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire (subscale emotional eating), and (D) Intuitive Eating Scale-2. Grey rhombus in panel A illustrates maintenance of BMI losses during four weeks follow-up. Groups did not differ on any measure before intervention. Error bars represent standard errors of the mean.

Trait food craving. There was a main effect of Time, $F(2,88)=12.7$, $p<.001$, $\eta_p^2=.225$, but no main effect of Group, $F(1,44)<1.00$. The Time effect was modulated by a Time \times Group interaction, $F(2,88)=15.0$, $p<.001$, $\eta_p^2=.254$. In the IG, craving decreased significantly between BL and T2, $MD=14.8$, $p<.001$, 95% CI [6.64, 23.0] as well as between BL and T3, $MD=22.3$, $p<.001$, 95% CI [13.7, 30.8], but not in the WG, both $MDs\leq 1.90$, both $ps=1.00$ (Figure 2B).

External, emotional, and intuitive eating. There was a main effect of Time for external eating, $F(2,88)=6.57$, $p=.004$, $\eta_p^2=.130$, but no main effect of Group, $F(1,39)<1.00$,

The Time effect was modulated by a Time×Group interaction, $F(2,88)=3.36, p=.047, \eta_p^2=.071$. External eating decreased significantly in the IG between BL and T2, $MD=6.17, p=.005, 95\% CI [1.59, 10.8]$ and between BL and T3, $MD=6.13, p=.002, 95\% CI [1.59, 10.8]$, but not in the WG, both $MDs \leq 1.10$, both $ps=1.00$. The same was found for emotional eating with a main effect of Time, $F(2,88)=11.3, p<.001, \eta_p^2=.205$, but no main effect of Group, $F(1,44) < 1.00$. The Time effect was modulated by a Time×Group interaction, $F(2,88)=7.00, p=.002, \eta_p^2=.137$. Emotional eating decreased significantly between BL and T2 in the IG, $MD=6.04, p=.001, 95\% CI [2.09, 10.0]$ and between BL and T3, $MD=9.13, p<.001, 95\% CI [4.74, 13.52]$, but not in the WG, both $MDs \leq 3.14$, both $ps \geq .160$ (Figure 2B).

In line with decreased external eating, intuitive eating revealed a main effect of Time, $F(2,88)=11.3, p<.001, \eta_p^2=.205$, but no main effect of Group, $F(1,44) < 1.00$. The Time effect was modulated by a Time×Group interaction, $F(2,88)=18.5, p<.001, \eta_p^2=.296$. In the IG, intuitive eating increased significantly between BL and T2, $MD=-0.41, p=.002, 95\% CI [-.686, -.131]$ as well as between BL and T3, $MD=-.837, p<.001, 95\% CI [-1.18, -.500]$, but not in the WG, both $MDs > -0.09$, both $ps=1.00$ (Figure 2D).

Discussion

This study is the first to examine effects of a short weight loss intervention that synergistically combines *MbT* with *PCh*. The intervention was expected to have a positive effect on weight as well as on eating styles (food craving, emotional and external eating, and intuitive eating). Results after completing the intervention were compelling: The intervention decreased BMI, and this loss was maintained during 4 weeks of follow-up. Importantly, also eating styles as central determinants of eating behavior showed advantageous changes: Individuals in the intervention group reported eating less often in response to negative emotions (emotional eating), or food cues/opportunity (external eating) but rather in response to hunger and satiety (intuitive eating). Participants in the IG further reported markedly reduced food

cravings, which is crucial because these are not only very frequent but they represent a central driver of non-homeostatic eating when experiencing hunger and deprivation (Richard, Meule, & Blechert, 2018), thereby often leading to diet failure (Meule, Richard, & Platte, 2017).

Study strengths include, first, a non-student sample of weight loss seeking, mostly overweight individuals, whereas previous studies were often limited to healthy university students (Warren et al., 2017). Second, we markedly moved away from classic weight loss treatments that stress calorie reduction and adopted a novel approach by combining two different techniques, *MbT* and *PCh*. These might be particularly synergistic in their interplay: *MbT* might have helped in supporting the focused and concentrated mindset during *PCh*, thereby enforcing *PCh* effects. At the same time, non-judgmental awareness is extended to the whole body and to emotions, thus reducing the ‘force’ behind emotional eating and binge eating episodes. By adopting this indirect and holistic approach, negative affect due to the pressure of having to lose weight might be avoided. Third, attrition rate, which is a mayor limitation of classic weight loss interventions (Yackobovitch-Gavan, Steinberg, Endevelt, & Benyamini, 2015), was very low. This might be due to short and compact intervention format (2 group and 2 individual sessions) and the swift weight loss early on.

Some limitations need to be mentioned: First, we relied on self-reported weight, which is prone to biases and inaccuracies. A standardized, blinded assessment might alter findings on weight reduction. Second, outcome measures were assessed by psychometric questionnaires only, while other measures could have offered convergent information, e.g. experimenter measured weight and food protocols. Novel assessment tools like (e.g., electromyogram-based eating detection; Blechert, Liedlgruber, Lender, Reichenberger, & Wilhelm, 2017) would provide objective and real-time on eating and, crucially – chewing behavior. Third, the mostly female sample might limit the generalizability of these findings. Future studies should aim for a replication in a larger sample with longer follow-up intervals. Assessment of eating disorders

should be undertaken as well as studies in more strictly defined samples (i.e. only obese, only eating disordered). Further, a comparison to other active treatment arms will reveal the relative effectiveness of this weight loss approach and rule out expectancies towards the intervention as a cause of observed changes. A decomposition of treatment components (only *MbT*, only *PCh*) will shed light on their individual contribution to treatment success.

In sum, *MbT* and *PCh* might help in ameliorating the effects of the modern life-style, with its erosion of meal times, time pressure, stressful multitasking, and its constant exposure to low quality snack foods on eating behavior by making mealtime a relaxing, conscious and positively valenced experience. It may further serve as an intervention for individuals with weight problems or binge eating symptoms, without the partially stigmatizing, weight loss- and deficit-oriented spirit of conventional weight loss programs.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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